

HERMAN RASSCHAERT

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Abstract: Herman Rasschaert's obedient submission to God's will makes him a herald of peace amidst communal violence. Amidst the worldly noise, he listens to God's voice and acts on it. His pastoral heart is large and open to God and the world. His resolute and bold step to involve in the urgent need of the time in favor of his neighbours culminates in the "shedding of his blood." His Spirit-enabled capacity to listen to the divine will, i.e., his obedience (*hypakoē*), is modeled on Jesus Christ's obedient submission to Abba. Hence, the ultimate disposition is: "Father, not my will but yours be done" (Lk 22:42).

Keywords: Herman Rasschaert, Obedience, *hypakoē*, Jesus-Witness, Communal Harmony.

INTRODUCTION

This series, titled "GOSPEL in ACTION," sheds light on Jesus' witnesses who by their deeds culminating in the "pouring out of blood" (cf. Lk 22:20) testify to the good news of the risen Lord Jesus Christ.¹ Herman Rasschaert is

¹ The twelve Jesus-witnesses introduced in the Series "GOSPEL in ACTION" in 2026 are: Devasahayam, Rani Maria, Kandhamal martyrs, Herman Rasschaert, Mathew Mannaparambil, John de Britto, James Kottayil, Stan Swamy, Arul Doss, AT Thomas, Valsa John, and Tom Gafney. Each of these twelve proclaims the Gospel with a Spirit-guided praxis. The *Acts of the Apostles* and *When the Gospel Grows Feet*, a biography on Rutilio Grande, inspire the series-title "GOSPEL in ACTION." In presenting each Jesus-witness, there is (1) a brief

Jesus' obedient witness. His pastoral heart leads him to seek the divine will and to share God's love with his people of all faiths among the tribals of Chotanagpur.

1. AN OBEDIENT WITNESS

On 24 March 1964, Tuesday of the Holy Week, Herman Rasschaert "walked up and down his room in prayerful deliberation; then resolutely took his cycle. His catechist and teachers asked him not to go; he would be killed. He replied that he would not stand this injustice [Hindu-Muslim riot in Gerda near Kutungia in Simdega]; he was ready to die, if need be, to stop it."² Rasschaert's Spirit-directed move culminates in the "shedding of his blood" for communal peace.

Herman Rasschaert, a Belgian Jesuit missionary, is born on 13 September 1922 in the Netherlands. He enters the Jesuit novitiate in Drongen and decides to come to India as a missionary. Upon arriving at the Ranchi Mission on 3 December 1947, he devotes "all his time to the study of Hindi" at St. Stanislaus' College, Sitagarha.³ Realizing that "the theory classes alone would not suffice to pick up the spoken language, he decided to cycle every day to Hazaribagh to sit with children and attend some classes in the local mission school."⁴

introduction to the martyr and their contextual Gospel praxis, and (2) a concise exposition to a defining characteristic of witnessing (*martyria*).

² J. Van Troy, "Fr. Herman Rasschaert, S.J. (1922-1964): A Ranchi Jesuit, Martyr of Charity," in *To Chotanagpur with Love and Service: Pioneers in the Ranchi Jesuit Province*, ed. Peter Tete, Ignatian Commemoration Volume (Ranchi: Ranchi Jesuit Society, 1991), 89. See also J. Van Troy, "A Jesuit Martyr for Communal Peace: Fr. Herman Rasschaert (1922-1964)," in *Jesuit Profiles: Some Eminent Jesuits of South Asia*, ed. V. Lawrence Sundaram (Anand: Gujarat Sahitya Prakash, 1991), 343. I am grateful to Fr. Ignatius Tete SJ for guiding me during a pilgrimage to Gerda, the place of Rasschaert's martyrdom, on 13 June 2022 and for helping me access valuable resources on Rasschaert.

³ Cf. Louis Francken, *A Man of Humanity, A Man of God: Short Biography of Fr. Herman Rasschaert SJ Published on the Occasion of the 50th Anniversary of His Martyrdom* (Ranchi: Ranchi Jesuits, 2014), 25. See also Kulwant Minj, "Herman Rasschaert: Peacemaker among Religious Communities," *Jivan* (November 2020): 26.

⁴ Francken, *A Man of Humanity*, 25.

Rasschaert's enthusiasm to learn the local language well points to his missionary zeal in involving himself fully in the tribal community of Chotanagpur. He serves his people as a true shepherd engaging in pastoral ministry in Khunti, Torpa, Karra, and Kutungia. People of all faiths find a place in his heart because it has been both large and open to God and neighbour. Once, while at Karra, when the only chance for a sick person in danger of death was to be taken to the district hospital in Ranchi, Rassaert

resolutely put the nearly unconscious man on the bar of his bicycle and held him between his arms so that he would not fall. Then he set off in the darkness to Ranchi, a distance of 40 km... the man was admitted in the Sadar Hospital where the doctors gave proper treatment. The man recovered his health, and his life was saved thanks to the care, courage and strength of Fr. Herman. He was a true missionary, always ready to sacrifice his own comfort to save the life of others.⁵

In the beginning of March 1964 communal disturbances and conflicts erupt in the industrial centres of Jamshedpur and Rourkela due mainly to a violent confrontation between the Muslim population and the Hindus in East Pakistan (presently Bangladesh). These disturbances spread quickly to the interior villages. The region of Kutungia, where Rassaert serves as the parish priest, has also been badly affected. On 24 March 1964,

dressed in cassock, Rassaert sped to Gerda on his bicycle and reached the mosque in 20 minutes... Even as the attackers hurled stones and bricks at the hundreds of people huddled in the small enclosure, he told the Muslims not to fear. He then turned to the crowd of attackers with these words, 'killing people is a grave sin! Stop this madness!' ... a boulder landed on his head. He fell on his knees. While he tried to rise in vain, more blows with sharp weapons did him to death.⁶

⁵ Ibid., 52.

⁶ Louis Francken, Aurel Brys, Cyprian Ekka, and Marianus Kujur, "Fr. Herman Rassaert, Messenger of Peace," in *Jesuits 2016: Yearbook of the Society of*

Thus culminates Rasschaert's Spirit-animated move to douse the Hindu-Muslim riot in Gerda with the "shedding of his blood."

"It would have been out of his character, if my son were not to die as he did!' – this spontaneous response of Julian Rasschaert to the news about his son Herman's violent death best sums up the latter's supreme sacrifice for communal harmony amidst communalization of politics and religion in India."⁷ Half a century ago, a 42-year-old humanitarian gives up his life trying to make rioters in [Gerda near Kutungia in] Simdega see reason. He fails then, but his martyrdom impinges itself on the community's conscience.⁸ In our times, his legacy of communal harmony is of immense relevance.

The inaugural ceremony of the diocesan inquiry of the cause of beatification and canonization of the Servant of God Fr. Herman Rasschaert is held in the Cathedral of Simdega Catholic diocese on 25 August 2019. In the same opening ceremony, Bishop Vincent Barwa appoints a board of inquiry to examine witnesses in order to discover the truth about the life, martyrdom and reputation of martyrdom of the Servant of God existing until the present day.⁹

2. *HYPAKOĒ* (OBEDIENCE)

Jesus' testimony to Abba springs from his disposition manifest in his Gethsemane prayer: "Father, not my will but yours be done" (Lk 22:42).¹⁰ The earliest such expression in Luke is

Jesus, ed. Giuseppe Bellucci (Roma: General Curia SJ, 2015), 88.

⁷ Francken, Brys, Ekka, and Kujur, "Fr. Herman Rasschaert, Messenger of Peace," 88.

⁸ Cf. Rudra Biswas, "He cycled to save mankind - Cardinal prays for priest who paid for peace with life," *The Telegraph*, https://www.telegraphindia.com/jharkhand/he-cycled-to-save-mankind-cardinal-prays-for-priest-who-paid-for-peace-with-life/cid/193799#goog_rewarded (accessed on 20.02.2026).

⁹ Cf. Kulwant Minj, "Fr. Herman Rasschaert SJ, the Servant of God: Update on the Beatification Process," in *Ranchi Jesuits: Yearbook 2020*, ed. Ajit K. Xess (Ranchi: Ranchi Jesuit Society, 2020), 17.

¹⁰ Jesus' prayer of total submission is addressed to the Father. According to Fitzmyer, "the n. *thelēma* [will] refers to the Father's plan of salvation for

when Jesus responds to his parents as they find him in the Temple: “I must be (*dei*) in my Father’s house” (Lk 2:49).¹¹ Jesus’ deliberate march toward the culmination of his witness in Jerusalem is a consequence of such obedience (*hypakoē*).¹² His each step toward Jerusalem is a step of obedient self-offering.

The cup of suffering that Jesus accepts (cf. Lk 22:42) and the subsequent path of obedience make him “a model of innocent suffering.”¹³ His obedient submission in Gethsemane is preparatory for the same on the cross. Besides, it makes clear that the object of submission is to do the Father’s will. Testifying to his death, the centurion affirms with certainty that “this man [Jesus] was innocent [righteous *dikaios*]” (Lk 23:47). Luke’s use of *dikaios* can better be rendered “righteous,” instead of “innocent” (NRSV).¹⁴

humanity... this part of the Lucan Jesus’ prayer expresses his basic filial orientation and submission.” Joseph A. Fitzmyer, *The Gospel according to Luke X–XXIV: Introduction, Translation, and Notes*, vol. 2, Anchor Yale Bible 28A (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2008), 1442. Luke emphasizes the significance of “hearing” (*akouō*) in Luke-Acts in terms of obedience to the divine will.

¹¹ Fitzmyer comments that “this is the first use of the impersonal *dei*, ‘it is necessary,’ in the Lucan Gospel. It expresses not only a necessity in general, but the peculiar Lucan connotation of what had to be as part of the Father’s salvific plan involving Jesus.” Joseph A. Fitzmyer, *The Gospel according to Luke X–XXIV: Introduction, Translation, and Notes*, vol. 1, Anchor Yale Bible 28A (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2008), 443. Jesus aligns his will to that of the Father by listening to the Father’s will and acting accordingly. This “divine necessity” (*dei*), that is the core of his obedience, is repeated in the passion predictions (Lk 9:22, 44-45; 18:31-34).

¹² According to Gerhard Kittel, “*hypakoē* is always used [in the NT] in connection with religious decision... is measured by the attitude of obedience to God.” Cf. “ὕπακοή [*hypakoē*],” *TDNT* 1:224. Luke structures the Gospel as an intentional journey to Jerusalem. The phrase “set his face” (Lk 9:51) evokes the image of the obedient Suffering Servant (cf. Isa 50:7).

¹³ Cf. Martin Dibelius, *From Tradition to Gospel*, trans. Bertram L. Wolf (New York, NY: Charles Scribner’s Sons, 1935), 201. Dibelius understands Luke’s presentation of Jesus’ passion as “martyrdom.” He comments that “for Luke, the suffering Saviour is the Man of God who is attacked by evil powers and who, with His patience and forgiveness is a model of innocent [righteous] suffering... The literary consequence of this view is that Luke presents the Passion as a martyrdom.” *Ibid.*

¹⁴ Though “Jesus’ innocence is a major theme of the passion narrative (23:4, 14, 15, 22, 41),” Johnson comments that “the term *δίκαιος* [*dikaios*] has the deeper

Jesus' example of "righteous suffering," as a result of obedience, is the basis both to temper one's view on sufferings and for overcoming struggles. In obedience, he testifies to the Father. After his earthly mission sealed ultimately with death, the Father makes him emerge victorious with resurrection.¹⁵ The resurrection is the apex of his faithful witness through "obedience" (*hypakoē*). It is the memory of this victory of Jesus, the "witness" (*martyr*), that "enables and emboldens others to follow in his footsteps."¹⁶

Herman Rasschaert's obedient submission to Lord Jesus Christ, subsequent to his prayerful deliberation, disposes him to venture out boldly to respond to the rioting faith-communities in Gerda. His obedience, i.e., his manner of listening to Christ's will, is an essential dimension of his witness.¹⁷ Like his teacher, who testifies to ultimate obedience to God through the surrender on the cross with the words, "Father, into your hands I commend my spirit" (Lk 23:46), Rasschaert's discernment prepares him to submit to Lord Jesus Christ.

religious significance of 'righteous.'" Luke T. Johnson, *The Gospel of Luke*, Sacra Pagina 3 (Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 1991), 382.

¹⁵ Jürgen Roloff notes that Jesus "fulfilled the message given to him with the obedience of his whole person and sealed this work with his death." Jürgen Roloff, *A Continental Commentary: The Revelation of John* (Minneapolis, MN: Fortress Press, 1993), 24.

¹⁶ Seán Freyne affirms that the only application of *martyr* to Jesus in the NT, in Rev 1:5, celebrates the ultimate victory of Jesus. For Freyne, the book of Revelation is "a document that celebrates the victory of Jesus, the faithful witness/martyr' (*pistos martyr*)." Seán Freyne, "Jesus the Martyr," *Concilium* 39/1 (2003): 57. The author of Revelation seeks to encourage the persecuted "Christians of Asia Minor who in c. 90 CE suffered at the hands of the Roman emperor, Domitian... By daringly recalling and celebrating his victory, Jesus the witness/martyr enables and emboldens others to follow in his footsteps. This was the pattern of Christian resistance..." Ibid.

¹⁷ Cf. Kittel, "ὑπακοή [*hypakoē*]," *TDNT*, 1:224. In the OT, "hearing is critical for the interaction between God and human beings; the medium through which God makes his will known among his people (in commandments or mediated by the prophets) is the audible word." Udo Rüterswörden, "שמע [*šm*]," *TDOT* 15:258.

CONCLUSION

Witnessing to the gospel of Lord Jesus Christ, Herman Rasschaert remains an envoy of peace and a paradigm of communal harmony. In the pluri-religious context of Chotanagpur, this young missionary spends his life selflessly as an obedient and Christ-like shepherd. His blood shed in Gerda, in defending many lives, testifies to the obedient submission to God's will. His *martyria* continues to bear abundant fruit in terms of peace, justice, and universal fraternity.

Book Reviews

Book Review Editor: Anil D'Almeida SJ

The Formation of Indian Seminarians at Sacred Heart Seminary, Poonamallee, Tamil Nadu – The Role of Mgr. Louis Mathias SDB (1935-1965). By Hendry Selvaraj Dominic. Roma: LAS, 2025. ISBN: 9-788821-316302. Pp. 481. Price: € 35.

The book studies the role of Msgr. Louis Mathias, SDB and the Sacred Heart Seminary (SHS), Poonamallee in the formation of Indian seminarians. The author, who has a doctorate from the Gregorian University, Rome, is currently a member of the Salesian Institute of History, Rome and of the Association of Salesian Historians (ACCSA), besides teaching at the Salesian Pontifical University and elsewhere.

Mathias has been described by historian Joseph Thekkedath as the greatest Salesian of the 20th century in India. The period under study, which coincides with Mathias' service as archbishop (1935–1965),

is marked by the emergent reality of independent India on the one hand, and the Second Vatican Council on the other.

Part A situates Mathias' option for the formation of a native clergy within its political, socio-economic and religious background. Native clergy did exist in both *Padroado* and *Propaganda* jurisdictions but were hampered by colonial prejudices. Under direction from Rome, the Synod of Pondicherry (1844) had opted to replace the "Malpanate" with the seminary system. It is against this background that Mathias established the Poonamallee seminary and asked the Salesians to run it.

Part B deals with the foundation and early years of SHS. The seminary had been already projected by Mathias' predecessor, Msgr. Eugène Mederlet. Mathias took up the project with enthusiasm and brought his considerable